

THE ORDERS OF INSECTS

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In order to understand the evolutionary position of the Lepidoptera, one needs to study at least cursorily all the main forms of insects. The Class Insecta (animals with 6 legs on the thorax, distinct head with antennae, and abdomen with 11 segments originally) has been divided into various numbers of orders according to different authors. Linne, in 1758, recognized 6 orders, whereas Handlirsch and Brues & Melander have accepted as many as 34. In the present list we recognize 23 orders. On page 47 is a phylogenetic chart showing the writer's version of the probable relationships of the orders. The orders and higher groups of insects are listed and defined below.

- A. Subclass APTERYGOTA (SYNAPTERA). (True Wingless Insects)
Contains all insects which have never had wings. Moulting continues after reproduction begins. Abdominal styli always present. Small, inconspicuous, nocturnal insects.
1. Order ENTOTROPHI. (Campodeids, Japygids, etc.)
No eyes; whitish cuticle; two tail filaments or forceps; mouthparts concealed; subterranean.
 2. Order THYSANURA. (Silverfish, Rock-jumpers)
Usually with eyes and scales; three caudal filaments; mouthparts exposed; only scaleless forms (nicoletiids) subterranean; some common in houses.
- B. Subclass PTERYGOTA. (True Winged Insects)
Contains all insects with wings or descended from winged ancestors. Moulting stops before reproduction begins. No conspicuous abdominal styli; usually none at all. The most successful members of the Animal Kingdom, occupying nearly every possible habitat; about 600,000 species.
- a. Division PALEOPTERA. (Ancient Winged Insects)
Wings can not be folded back and rested flat on abdomen (primitive hinge mechanism only). Nymphs always aquatic. Once prominent; now only two living orders remain.
 3. Order ODONATA. (Dragonflies & Damselflies)
Nymphs with caudal or rectal gills. Adults predacious; with 2 prs. similar net-veined wings; eyes very large; antennae tiny; copulatory organs of ♂ on 2nd and 3rd abd. segments; no moult after fully winged stage reached.
 4. Order EPHEMERIDA (PLECOPTERA). (Mayflies)
Nymphs with lateral gills. Adults non-feeding, short-lived; with 2 prs. net-veined wings, hind pr. small; eyes large; antennae tiny; copulatory organs of ♂ terminal, paired; 2 or 3 long tail filaments; one moult after fully winged stage (subimago) reached.
 - b. Division NEOPTERA. (Modern Winged Insects)
Wings with special hinge mechanism, permitting them to be laid flat on abdomen at rest. Now the most successful group in the Animal Kingdom, occupying nearly every possible habitat; about 600,000 species known.
 - aa. Section HEMIMETABOLA. (Incomplete Metamorphosis)
Immature stage (nymph) similar in appearance and usually habits to adults (but lacking full wings, of course). No pupal stage. Wings develop externally.
 5. Order PLECOPTERA (PERLARIA). (Stoneflies)
Nymphs aquatic, flat, with long antennae, 2 long tail filaments (cerci). Adults with long antennae; hind wings large, fan-like, carried flat on abdomen at rest; 2 tail filaments (often short).
 6. Order EMBIOPTERA. (Embiids)
Nymphs terrestrial; enlarged front tarsi (for spinning); flattened; chewing mouthparts; cerci short; ♀ wingless; ♂ wings all alike; colonial; under stones, wood, soil, etc.
 7. Order DERMAPTERA. (Earwigs & Hemimerids)
Strong pincers on abdomen. Wings much like Orthoptera but forewings short; eyes present; cuticle hard, not white; nocturnal.
 8. Order ORTHOPTERA. (Grasshoppers, Grylloblattids, Roaches, Praying Mantids, Walking Sticks, etc.)
Fore wings narrow and leathery (many wingless); hind wings large, fan-like, covered by fore wings at rest; chewing mouthparts; cerci short or long, usually segmented; nearly all eat vegetation, mantids carnivorous.
 9. Order ISOPTERA. (Termites)
Social insects, winged only for swarming to found new colonies; workers wingless, soft, whitish; chewing mouthparts; wings all similar; cerci short; galleries connected to vegetable food source, often dead wood.
 10. Order PSOCOPTERA (CORRODENTIA). (Book Lice, Psocids, Zorapterans)
Very small; wings (when present) all membranous, with large stigma and few veins; at rest wings folded roof-like over abdomen; tarsi with 2 or 3 joints; cerci tiny or absent; antennae long; chewing mouthparts; living on plants, in paper, in dead wood.
 11. Order THYSANOPTERA. (Thrips)
Very small, slender; mouthparts forming short, piercing beak; antennae short, thick; all wings narrow straps with fringe of long hairs; wings flat on abdomen at rest; tarsi with exsertile vesicle at tips; on vegetation, fungi, wood. Thrips have pseudo-pupal stage before maturity.

12. Order ANOPLURA. (Bird Lice, Sucking Lice)
Always wingless, but ancestors presumably winged; horizontally flattened; mouthparts for chewing or as short beak for sucking; antennae short; eyes inconspicuous; claws specialized for travel on hairs and feathers; no cerci; all external parasites of mammals & birds.
13. Order HEMIPTERA. (True Bugs, Aphids, Scales, etc.)
Fore wings usually thickened in fore half or entirely; mouthparts as long piercing & sucking proboscis, held backwards under head at rest; many herbivorous, some carnivorous.
- bb. Section HOLOMETABOLA. (Complete Metamorphosis)
Immature active (feeding) stage (larva) not resembling adult at all. Non-feeding maturation stage (pupa) between larva and imago. Wings develop internally.
14. Order COLEOPTERA. (Beetles, Weevils)
Fore wings very hard, entirely shell-like, at rest covering large, much folded membranous hind wings; mouthparts very diverse, sometimes on rostrum, but always of chewing type; in most aquatic & terrestrial habitats.
15. Order STREPSIPTERA. (Stylopids)
Minute; fore wings of ♂ reduced to small club, hind wings fan-like; ♂ antennae finger-like; ♀ larviform, always wingless; internal parasites of bees, wasps, leaf hoppers, silverfish; very rare.
16. Order HYMENOPTERA. (Sawflies, Ants, Bees, Wasps)
All 4 wings membranous; hind wings smaller and with anterior row of hooks for coupling with fore wings; wings often absent; mouthparts for chewing except in bees (sucking); ovipositor always present in ♀, sometimes as sting; larva usually legless; sawfly larvae much like Lepidoptera larvae but lack hooks on abdominal legs; pupae usually in silk cocoon; plant feeders, endoparasites, carnivores, etc.
17. Order MEGALOPTERA. (Alderflies & Dobsonflies)
All wings similar, many-veined, held roof-like or flat over abdomen at rest; long antennae; no cerci; very soft abdomen; larvae aquatic, with biting mouthparts; pupae always terrestrial, in mud cell.
18. Order NEUROPTERA. (Ant-lions, Lacewings, etc.)
All wings similar, many-veined, held roof-like over abdomen at rest; wing veins notably forked near tips; antennae short & knobbed or long; no cerci; abdomen soft; larvae usually terrestrial, with mouthparts for piercing & sucking, highly predacious; pupae in silk cocoon.
19. Order MECOPTERA. (Scorpion-flies)
Chewing mouthparts on tip of long beak; all wings similar, often with markings; antennae long; legs long; cerci short; ♂ genitalia usually conspicuous, often "scorpion-like"; larvae caterpillar-like, in soil, lack hooks on abdominal legs.
20. Order TRICHOPTERA. (Caddis-flies)
Moth-like, but wings hairy (few or no scales); wings always roof-like over abdomen at rest; mouthparts not capable of feeding, much reduced; antennae long; larvae and pupae always aquatic; larvae usually in case, have 1 pr. hook-bearing anal legs; pupae with strong mandibles, often active.
21. Order LEPIDOPTERA. (Moths & Butterflies)
All 4 wings membranous, few cross veins, heavily clothed with scales (wings rarely absent); antennae long; mouthparts usually suctorial, composed of maxillae; mandibles usually absent; larvae usually caterpillar-shaped; abdominal legs with hooks or crochets; pupae essentially inactive.
22. Order DIPTERA. (True Flies, Mosquitoes, etc.)
Only 1 pr. wings; 2nd pr. reduced to club-like halteres with gyroscopic function in flight; wings never heavily scaled nor very hairy; mouthparts very diversified, usually suctorial; metathorax very small; larvae aquatic or terrestrial, plant or animal feeders or parasites, legless, head rarely well-developed; pupa inactive and enclosed in last larval skin or active and free.
23. Order SIPHONAPTERA. (Fleas)
Small, strongly flattened vertically; no wings; antennae short, in grooves along head; piercing and sucking mouthparts; adults external parasites of mammals and birds; larvae long, legless, pale, living in trash; pupae in cocoons.

Several groups sometimes considered orders are not so accepted in the above list. The ZORAPTERA fit well in the Order PSOCOPTERA. The PHASMATODEA (Walking Sticks), MANTODEA (Praying Mantids), BLATTARIA (Roaches), and GRYLLOBLATTODEA are satisfactory suborders of the Order ORTHOPTERA. The MALLOPHAGA (Bird Lice) differ in no essential characters from the Sucking Lice and are combined with them in the Order ANOPLURA. The HOMOPTERA (Scales, Aphids, Cicadas, etc.) are not different from the True Bugs in ordinal characters and remain in the HEMIPTERA. The DIPLOGLOSSATA (Hemimerids) are merely highly modified DERMAPTERA. The ZEUGLOPTERA (Micropterygids) do not seem separable from the LEPIDOPTERA.

There is some doubt as to the desirability of separating the STREPSIPTERA from the COLEOPTERA and the MEGALOPTERA from the NEUROPTERA, but the above arrangement is satisfactory for present purposes.

The COLLEMBOLA (Springtails) and the PROTURA (Telson-tails) are usually included in the Insecta, but the evidence seems clear that the COLLEMBOLA are well separated from the insects and must form a group of their own, probably below the Myriapods. The PROTURA are too little known and perhaps too degenerate for definite placement, but they differ from insects in some fundamental ways. Both groups have been included in the Insecta chiefly because they possess three pairs of legs.

PHYLOGENETIC CHART OF THE ORDERS OF INSECTS

